

PHYSICAL CULTURE AND HEALTH IN ABU BAKR RAZI'S TEACHING

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Shamuratova Barno Yuvbasarovna

senior lecturer of the "sport activities"

department of UrSU

Physical activity is the use of various types of physical activity by people in order to maintain and strengthen their health. Many scholars have expressed their important opinions about physical culture.

In particular, Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Zakariya Razi acquired many sciences and focused his attention on medicine. His first teacher in medicine was Ali ibn Zain Tabari, the author of the first dictionary in this field, "Firdavsul Hikma".

Abu Bakr ArRazi was one of the most prominent representatives of Islamic civilization in his time in terms of physical education, medicine. He was the leader in the establishment of a hospital in the city of Ray, and later led doctors in a hospital in Baghdad. He was the first to use chemical compounds in medical procedures and wrote a treatise on childhood disease. He was the first to use animal intestines instead of thread in surgery. He studied smallpox, measles, and various hereditary diseases, and in the course of his medical-scientific research, he first conducted experiments on animals.

In addition to medicine, Razi thoroughly studied chemistry and (botany) related to it. He also paid great attention to philosophy. Because most of the Greek philosophers also talked about medicine. His first teacher in philosophy was Balkhi. In this way, Razi devoted most of his life to the study of medical sciences and achieved great success.(1.)

According to Aruzi Samarkandi, who lived in the 12th century, Razi also came to Bukhara and cured the Samanid ruler of paralysis. He had a close relationship with Bukhara scholars. Among his students, he mentions the great Bukhara scientist Muhammad ibn Yunus with special respect and dedicates two of his great works on chemistry to him.

He returned to the city of Ray and was appointed as the director of the hospital. It was one of the first major hospitals in Islam. After Razi treated and cured patients suffering from serious diseases, the disease spread to the surrounding area. His name even reached Azidoud Dawla ibn Buwayh, one of the ministers of the Abbasid state. The minister summoned him to Baghdad and

appointed him as the chairman of doctors at Azudi Hospital. This hospital was the largest hospital in the world at that time, and 50 doctors worked there. In addition to being a hospital, this dargah served as a medical university at the highest level.(3)

During his lifetime, scholars translated the medical books of the Greeks, Persians, Indians, and Egyptians. Razi read them, studied them, conducted experiments and made the necessary conclusions.

At that time, the science of medicine was widely developed in the Greeks. But they limited themselves to theories and paid little attention to practice. All Greek physicians were known for their medical philosophy.

Razi has a famous saying that has not lost its relevance to this day. "When there is a conflict between scientific theory and practical work, it is necessary to choose the practice seen in reality, even if it is a theory supported by any famous scholars!" He never preferred other theories except when a scientist, famous or not famous, conducted a scientific experiment and then came to a conclusion about it. Perhaps, rather than controversial hypotheses, he considered it preferable because the conclusions and results of scientific experiments are clear. Razi first conducted scientific experiments on animals and developed strong skills. Medicines were first used in monkeys, and if the tests were successful, he recommended them to humans. Medicines are first tested on animals, as Razi does now.

Several such experiments, which were first carried out by Razi, are still widely used in modern medicine.

Razi is not limited to a certain field of medicine. He focused on internal medicine, diseases of children and women, treatment of eye and genital diseases and surgery.

In fact, Allah Almighty had given him a high intellect. This can also be seen from the choice of a suitable place for the establishment of a large hospital in Baghdad. When told to point out a place for a hospital, he is moving fresh meat around to different places at the same time in four directions. After a certain period of time, he examines the meats and finally chooses the place where the meat is rotten and builds a hospital there. The reason for this behavior is that the meat is stored for a long time in a place with clean air. Patients recover faster in clean air.

Apart from being a skilled doctor, Razi was also a great teacher who taught his knowledge and experiences. He organized a community of science in a madrasa near Azudi Hospital in Baghdad and taught medical science to students. Razi started teaching in two different ways: scientific-theoretical and practical experience. He gave theoretical knowledge to the students first. Then he prepared

for practice step by step. After three years, he examined students in two stages: surgery and treatment of various diseases. Students who did not pass the first stage were not allowed to the next stage.

In addition to treating patients and teaching, Razi managed to write many books. Ibn Nadim mentioned in his book "al-Fihrist" that he wrote 113 books and 68 treatises. All of these voluminous works were related to medicine.

He has written several books on the diagnosis and treatment of the disease. "Risalatul fil jadari wal hasba" (Treatise on Smallpox and Measles), "Kitab al-asrar" (Book of Secrets), "Al-kitab al-jame'" (Collective book) are among them.

Razi's book is called "Kitab at-tib al-Mansuri", named after the governor of Khurasan, Mansur ibn Ishaq. This book provides information on surgery, internal medicine and eye diseases. He wrote the book "At-tibar-rohani" about reforming the soul, developing the mind, controlling passions and refraining from bad habits.

He advised his students to write down ideas that were not written in previous books in the process of learning and treatment, and he himself followed that. Therefore, many innovations are found in his works and books.

As another example of Razi's great attention to the issue of ethics, the book "Akhloqut tabib" can be cited. In it, he writes about how a doctor should treat others, especially a patient or a doctor like himself, and how a patient should treat doctors. The culture of treatment strengthens a person's self-confidence in overcoming illness, and it shows that it is of great importance for the recovery of the patient. . He determined the level of physical activity of the patients and then recommended healthy physical activities, which means that every person will be healthy if he is physically active.

In fact, Abu Bakr Muhammad ibn Zakariyya Razi, as a great scientist and a skilled doctor, served the development of Islamic civilization and the whole world of medical science and left a great legacy.

In fact, young men and women who are healthy on all fours, plump, and beaming from their faces are the beauty of any nation. When you see them, your eyes are happy, your heart is happy, you are proudfull of pride. Our wise people have been honoring and honoring physical health since time immemorial. In this regard, our people have learned wonderful medical wisdom: "A healthy body is wealth", "A healthy body is a healthy mind", "All the blessings of the world cannot be equal to health" and many others. Concepts and ideas about physical health and the struggle for a healthy generation have been different in different regions and nations since ancient times. But no matter what, the people and the people rarely looked at these issues carelessly and indifferently. It is true that people did not live

as long as they wanted in all times. Most of the time, this noble dream has remained as an intention, wishful thinking. But the important thing is that in the distant past, people realized that health and longevity are related to many social, economic, spiritual and political factors. The ancient Greeks, who lived long before Christ, not only dreamed of living a long life, but also succeeded in achieving it. According to Plato, most of them lived up to 180-200 years. The secret of this was believed by the ancients to be a moral belief, a conscientious, and above all a healthy way of life. In this context, those who live a very short life, i.e. 70 years, face the wrath of the creator because of poor diet, lack of physical activity and lack of healthy lifestyle. Those who passed away at this age thought that they had done something wrong. Average life expectancy is estimated at 200 years (modern medical science also recognizes that the natural physiological aging of the human body occurs only after reaching the age of 100. Early life is still considered unnatural). The pledge of long life, the ancients knew how to live life with fresh air, physical exercise, freedom, good manners, politeness, grace and humility, and many people determined the limits of life by following these or not. Galen lived 140 years, Sophocles lived 130 years, Socrates lived 106 years, Hippocrates lived 104 years. Naturally, the fact that they know health is a great value and strive for it played a big role in this. At the present time, there are such long-lived people. If we observe the life activities of those who have reached the age of 100-107, they live a healthy lifestyle, confident in the future and in constant physical activity. many have linked the life limits with whether or not to follow them. Galen lived 140 years, Sophocles lived 130 years, Socrates lived 106 years, Hippocrates lived 104 years. Naturally, the fact that they know health is a great value and strive for it played a big role in this. At the present time, there are such long-lived people. If we observe the life activities of those who have reached the age of 100-107, they live a healthy lifestyle, confident in the future and in constant physical activity. many have linked the life limits with whether or not to follow them. Galen lived 140 years, Sophocles lived 130 years, Socrates lived 106 years, Hippocrates lived 104 years. Naturally, the fact that they know health is a great value and strive for it played a big role in this. (3) At the present time, there are such long-lived people. If we observe the life activities of those who have reached the age of 100-107, they live a healthy lifestyle, confident in the future and in constant physical activity.

Razi said, "The highest goal of human life is to achieve happiness. A person's happiness depends on his health, will, meaningful life. "If a person strives for mental perfection just as he strives for high physical perfection, he will undoubtedly achieve the happiness he seeks."

Physical beauty is important in human development. Being physically fit and healthy is not only a personal but also a social value.

Abu Bakr Razi glorified human intelligence, encouraged people to study natural phenomena and acquire science, build a happy life, and rationally enjoy all the pleasures of material and spiritual life. Razi's socio-ethical views are also noteworthy. He noted that "excess wealth leads to injustice in the world." There should be a "moderate norm" for members of society. The great judge also thought about the dignity of a person. According to him, the value of each person is determined by how much benefit he brings to society. A person becomes useful to the society when he becomes a mentally and physically perfect person.(2)

Youth sports and physical labor should be regularly engaged with. Physical activity increases the level of endomorphin in the body - hormones that cause pleasant situations and good moods. A good way to boost your mood is to exercise more. Physical exercise has been proven to be of great benefit when the mind and body are tired. Razi was the first to organize "The History of Disease" in Iran. 36 of his medical works have come down to us. He has several works on healthy lifestyles in feeding and caring for infants and toddlers. Razi's works "On Child Education" and "Children's Diseases" have been translated into many foreign languages. These works were considered a scientific and practical guide to Eastern and Western medicine.

According to Razi, it is well known that a person's health is influenced by the world around him. Metabolic processes occurring in our body are positively and negatively affected not only by major problems in society, but also by simple relationships between people. Also, various chemical substances and physical factors have a strong influence on the health of a person.

According to the Razi method, if we want to fully understand the processes occurring in the body and influence them, no matter how difficult it may be, we should not ignore any factor that can be the cause of the disease. In fact, many factors (physical, chemical, spiritual, etc.) affect the body. Therefore, in order to achieve the goal, it is necessary to consider the problem from all sides. For example, if a person is always in a state of strong nervous excitement (stress) (at home or at work), in spite of all the treatment, let's say, in the case of gastric ulcer, because the main cause (stress) is not eliminated, he will not be able to get rid of the disease in the future. In this case, the development of the disease is mainly caused by personal or social relationships.(4)

Razi's research suggests that eye strain is caused by more reading, especially in dim light. In fact, reading is one of the best ways to keep the eyes active and

healthy, and no matter how much a person reads, it will never cause vision impairment. Only if the eye is not always in a situation that causes excessive strain.

Razi should understand that normal sighted people can read without worry in any light, but visually impaired people, especially those who wear glasses, strain their eyes every time they read. However, one of the best ways for visually impaired people to regain normal vision is to force themselves to read for a certain period of time every day (without wearing glasses, of course). If the study is done correctly, it can only bring good results, but if it continues as usual, the work will turn out to be worse than before. If people's mental exercises lead to the expansion of brain activity, physical culture is considered the main tool for physical recovery.

In short, Razi's legacy is one of the guiding stars in youth physical culture.

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